

Alternative Work Arrangements: Its Relationship to Work Values and Its Work- Life Balance

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Abstract. This study aimed to explore the impact of work values and work-life balance on the alternative work arrangements of teachers. Utilizing a quantitative design with a correlational approach, the research involved 346 public elementary school teachers. The study employed mean, Pearson's r , and regression analysis to analyze the data. Adapted survey questionnaires were used to measure work values, work-life balance, and alternative work arrangements. The findings indicated that the levels of work values, work-life balance, and alternative work arrangements were all rated as "strongly agree." There was no significant relationship between work values and alternative work arrangements. However, a significant relationship was found between work-life balance and alternative work arrangements. Regression analysis further revealed that work-life balance had the most substantial influence on alternative work arrangements, as indicated by its highest beta coefficient. The study suggests that understanding the interplay between work values, work-life balance, and alternative work arrangements can benefit both employers and employees by fostering a more efficient working environment.

KEY WORDS

1. work values 2. work-life balance 3. alternative work arrangements

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1. Introduction

Teachers today face increasing pressure to achieve better results, as officials have heightened expectations (Tarraya, 2023). This study focuses on work arrangements, work values, and the work-life balance of teachers. Teachers often work long hours, constantly check emails, engage in continuous official communication late into the night, and work on their laptops even during holidays and weekends. Consequently, the most dedicated teachers struggle to balance their work and personal lives (Obasi Adieme, 2021). Achieving work-life balance allows individuals to manage resources to meet both family and work demands, enabling effective participation in both areas of life (Voydanoff, 2019). From an employee's perspective, it involves managing work obligations and personal family responsibilities. From an employer's perspective, it means fostering a supportive organizational culture where employees can focus on their jobs while at work. Work-life balance is about effectively managing the juggling act between paid work and other important activities, such as spending time with family, participating in sports and recreation, volunteering, or pursuing further studies (Grag-

nano et al., 2020). It can help build strong communities and productive businesses. Poor work-life balance has been identified as a cause of low work values and high levels of work-family conflict. A study in India found that the main causes of work imbalance were excessive working hours and inflexible work schedules (Gautam Jain, 2019). It was also discovered that work-life imbalance was a major source of dissatisfaction among teachers. Participants linked problems with work-life balance to withdrawal behaviors, including turnover and non-genuine sick absences (Susanto, 2022). These studies suggest that employers can improve work-life balance by implementing family-friendly initiatives such as flexi-time, time off, compressed workweeks, childcare support, and eldercare support (Shouman Vidal-Sune, 2022). While studies on alternative work arrangements, work values, and work-life balance have been conducted in foreign settings, similar research in the local context is lacking. Observing these issues in the workplace, this study aims to determine whether alternative work arrangements impact the relationship between work values and work-life balance. This could raise awareness among the intended beneficiaries and potentially lead to initiatives that improve teaching jobs and school management, highlighting the need for this research. Employee values towards their work can provide greater scheduling freedom through flexible work programs. This approach allows personnel to contribute effectively while managing their personal lives (Jayashree et al., 2023). It also encourages employees to develop innovative solutions to conflicts in their professional and personal lives. Alternative work arrangements offer workers more control over their work schedules, which can prevent dissatisfaction caused by an imbalance between work commitments and other responsibilities. Employees with a fair balance between work and family often feel a greater sense of responsibility and control. Support-

ive employers can benefit from increased loyalty and commitment from their subordinates, helping to retain talent and reduce turnover and recruitment costs (Rehman, 2020). Work-life balance has a significant relationship with alternative work arrangements. Some studies have found that many respondents feel confident in balancing their routine work while having alternative work arrangements. Conversely, some teachers struggle to balance work due to economic and family problems, inefficiency, and lack of commitment. Long working hours, compulsory overtime, stress-related job activities, and inflexible schedules can lead to absenteeism, turnover, frustration, low morale, and motivation, ultimately causing work-life imbalance (Kanthi, 2019). Factors affecting work-life balance include partner support, colleague support, and job resources, which are positively associated with work-life balance, while unfair criticism at work is negatively associated (Fatima, 2021). Flexible work programs provide employees with greater scheduling freedom, allowing them to fulfill their job obligations more effectively (Siddiqui Rehman, 2022). Research by Cameron and Garret (2019) revealed that work values are strengthened through alternative work arrangements, leading to improved morale and productivity. Employees performed excellently and prioritized completing tasks on time. Another study found that alternative work arrangements among teachers reduced stress, as they could meet work demands from the comfort of their homes without worrying about working conditions and long hours (Madipelli, 2019). This study emphasized that such arrangements foster close relationships with family, positive attitudes, and cooperation. While much of the existing research focuses on broader organizational benefits or productivity outcomes, there is limited exploration of how individual work values, personal priorities, and unique life circumstances influence an employee's choice of alternative work arrangements. Moreover,

the personal impact of these arrangements on achieving a healthy work-life balance, particularly in terms of emotional well-being, family responsibilities, and personal fulfillment, remains underexplored. Addressing this gap could provide deeper insights into how alternative work arrangements can be tailored to better meet the diverse needs and values of employees, ultimately leading to more meaningful and effective work-life balance solutions. The main purpose of this study was to determine whether alternative work arrangements mediate the relationship between work values and work-life balance of teachers. The first objective was to describe the level of work values of teachers in terms of intrinsic values, organization-man ethic values, upward striving, and social status of the job, conventional ethics, and attitudes towards earnings. The second objective was to ascertain the level of work-life balance in terms of satisfaction with family and self-life, role overload, awareness, job satisfaction, flexible environment, and self-appreciation of work. It also measured the level of alternative work arrangements. The study found a significant relationship between alternative work arrangements, work values, and work-life balance. Specifically, alternative work arrangements positively influence the relationship between work values and work-life balance. However, there was no significant relationship between alternative work arrangements, work values, and work-life balance. Alternative work arrangements do not influence the relationship between work values and work-life balance. Additionally, this study examined the significance of the relationships between work values and work-life balance, work values and alternative work arrangements, and alternative work arrangements and work-life balance. The overall findings indicated no significant relationship between work values and alternative work arrangements. This result aligns with the work of Kossek and Michel (2019), who noted that millennials are more likely to accept job of-

fers from companies that provide flexible work schedules, as this allows them to allocate time to other activities, including pursuing additional income streams.

1.1. Theoretical and Conceptual Framework —Studies have focused on alternative work arrangements as flexible working models widely used for continuity of work. For instance, a study investigating employees' attitudes and behaviors toward flexible working and a four-day work week found that alternative work arrangements positively impact socialization, happiness, stress levels, motivation, personal time, mental health, comfort, work-life balance, time-saving, willingness, positive working environment, and physical health (Yildizhan et al., 2023). In another study, the effects of alternative work arrangements on employees' exhaustion, work-non-work conflict, and job performance were examined among 17 different human service organizations in Germany. It was found that the negative impact of time restrictions outweighs the positive outcomes of time autonomy on work-non-work conflict, making work values an important indicator for practitioners in human resource management (Kattenbach et al., 2019). Similarly, work-life balance affects alternative work arrangements among teachers. Alternative work arrangements contribute to the work-life balance of teachers. Mechanisms of alternative work arrangements affect work-life balance, behavior, and organizational performance. It is important for teachers to participate in development activities because their continuous learning and ongoing development are essential for an organization's ability to adapt to the rapidly changing economy and society (Hurtz Williams, 2019; Beauregard Henry, 2019). This study was anchored on Alderfer's (1969) ERG theory, which considers the elements of needs and varies in approach because there are only three central needs: existence, relatedness, and the desire to grow as a human being. Applied to this study, the theory

associates alternative work arrangements and work-life balance. If a worker is dissatisfied with the existing work plan and feels it stifles their ability to grow, they experience imbalance. Thus, teachers can counteract levels of discontent by offering a work setup conducive to their needs (Eisbrenner, 2020). Another supporting theory is Clark's (2000) family/work border theory, which emphasizes that work-life balance is a wide-ranging concept involving proper prioritization between an employee's work and personal life. As shown in Figure 1, the independent variable in this study is work values, which is correlated with work-life balance, the dependent variable. Work values are determined by the following indicators: intrinsic values, organization-man ethic values, upward striving, social status of the job, conventional ethics, and attitudes towards earnings. The dependent variable in this study is alternative work arrangements, which refer to the identified work schedules of teachers reporting on-site. In the Department of Education, this has been implemented in various setups. Generally, in a global context, work-life balance is important as it

serves as a crucial aspect of a healthy work environment. Maintaining work-life balance helps reduce stress and prevent burnout in the workplace (Gagnano et al., 2020). Achieving work-life balance can improve employee productivity and lead to higher levels of work success (Wedgwood, 2020). Workers become more motivated to perform their tasks when their lives are balanced. The findings of this study may be particularly beneficial to the Department of Education personnel, school heads, teachers, students, and future researchers, as they highlight the importance of work-life balance in contributing positively to society rather than becoming a liability. This study contributes to the global discourse on work-life balance and alternative work arrangements by providing empirical evidence from the educational sector, particularly within the context of teachers. The findings may offer insights into how alternative work arrangements can be optimized to enhance work-life balance, potentially serving as a model for educational systems worldwide, especially in addressing the evolving demands of modern work environments.

2. Methodology

In this chapter, we will outline the processes and steps involved in conducting the study. This will encompass selecting the study's design, identifying the respondents and the sampling method, choosing the research instruments for data collection, and delineating the data analysis process. The researcher employed artificial intelligence methods to meticulously proofread this work during its preparation. Artificial Intelligence (AI) was expressly utilized to enhance the overall quality, coherence, and precision of the manuscript. This methodology is being openly communicated to adhere to ethical norms in research. Leveraging AI for proofreading underscores a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledges AI's growing role and potential in professional and academic writing.

2.1. Research Design—This research employed a quantitative, descriptive-correlational design to identify correlations between variables using multiple regression analysis. This structured approach involved collecting and analyzing data from various sources, utilizing com-

putational, statistical, and mathematical tools to derive results. The purpose was conclusive, aiming to quantify the problem and understand its prevalence by seeking projectable results for a larger population (Labaree, 2019). This research design was appropriate for the study as

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

it aimed to determine the mediating effect of alternative work arrangements on the relationship between work values and work-life balance. Additionally, the descriptive-correlational design was suitable because the variables—work values, work-life balance, and alternative work arrangements—were examined in their natural settings without manipulation or alteration (Belli, 2020). The correlational design was used to describe, explore, and explain the degree and strength of the relationships between alternative work arrangements and work-life balance, as well as between alternative work arrangements and work values.

2.2. Research Respondents—The respondents of this study consisted of 346 teachers from a total population of 515 in the Laak South District. These teachers were specifically selected based on their experience with alternative work arrangements. They were employed across various schools within the district and had implemented alternative work arrangements at different times throughout the school year, particularly in response to weather conditions and natural calamities that necessitated such measures. The researcher utilized a stratified random sampling technique to determine the number of respondents for the study, using Raosoft (2021). As a result, 67 of the teachers in the Laak South District participated in the survey. The inclusion criteria for this study were as follows: teachers from the Laak South District, as they were the most suitable respondents to provide useful information to test the hypothesis of this study. The qualifications included being public elementary school teachers within the Laak South District, having current or past experience with alternative work arrangements, and being willing to participate in the study. This study focused on alternative work arrangements, work values, and work-life balance, requiring teachers' perceptions and experiences in the teaching job. Excluded from the study were school heads, parents, students, and other

non-teaching staff. The researcher reserved the right to withdraw a respondent from the study if they committed falsification, plagiarism, or other moral offenses, or if they had health conditions and special needs. Participants could also withdraw from the study at any time if they felt troubled, discomforted, or uninterested. If so, participants were encouraged to inform the researcher of their wish to withdraw. Providing a reason for leaving the study was optional.

2.3. Research Instrument—The survey questionnaire used in this study consisted of three parts. The first part was adapted from Wollack, Goodale, and Smith's (2021) Work Values Questionnaire. A five-point Likert Scale was utilized to score each item, ranging from very high to very low. The original questionnaire was modified to fit the school setting, resulting in 25 item-statements. The questionnaire underwent pilot testing and was validated by a panel of experts. Suggestions and recommendations from the experts were integrated into the modified instrument. The following range of means was used to describe the level of work values: 4.20 – 5.00 (very high, meaning the work values item is observed at all times), 3.40 – 4.19 (high, meaning the work values item is often observed), 2.60 – 3.39 (moderate, meaning the work values item is sometimes observed), 1.80 – 2.59 (low, meaning the work values item is seldom observed), and 1.00 – 1.79 (very low, meaning the work values item is never observed). The Work Values Cronbach's Alpha was .932, with a Cronbach's Alpha based on standardized items of .931 and an N of 18 items, indicating high reliability. The second part of the survey was the Work Life Balance Questionnaire (Punah, Kamboj, VeenaLatha, 2019). It consisted of 25 items measuring five constructs: satisfaction with family and self-life, role overload, awareness, job satisfaction and flexible environment, and self-appreciation of work. The original questionnaire was modified to fit the school setting. Each item was scored using a

five-point Likert Scale ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree. Like the first part, this questionnaire underwent pilot testing and was validated by a panel of experts. Suggestions and recommendations from the experts were integrated into the modified instrument. The following range of means was used to describe the level of work-life balance: strongly agree to strongly disagree, indicating the extent to which the work-life balance item is manifested. The Work Life Balance Cronbach's Alpha was .945, with a Cronbach's Alpha based on standardized items of .943 and an N of 46 items, indicating high reliability. The third part of the instrument

was the Alternative Work Arrangement Questionnaire, adapted from Mas and Pallais (2019). It consisted of 20 items, and the original questionnaire was modified to fit the school setting. Each item was scored using a five-point Likert Scale ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree. Like the first and second parts, this questionnaire underwent pilot testing and was validated by a panel of experts. The Cronbach's Alpha was .886, with a Cronbach's Alpha based on standardized items of .943 and an N of 46 items. Suggestions and recommendations from the experts were integrated into the modified instrument.

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—In conducting the study, the researcher followed necessary steps starting in October 2022. Initially, permission was sought from the Dean of the Graduate School to officially acknowledge the research by the university. This approval was then sent to the Schools Division Superintendent, District Supervisor, and School Heads of the identified schools as venues for the study. The letter requested permission to conduct research on the influence of work values and work-life balance on teachers' alternative work arrangements. The Certificate of Approval, or Form 2.6, was sent via UMERC email to the researcher with UMERC number 2023-116. Upon receiving approval from the relevant personnel and the Informed Consent Form (ICF), the researcher personally encouraged teachers to participate in the study. The researcher distributed the questionnaire to the participants and ensured a 100 retrieval rate. A Certificate of Appearance was obtained from the school heads to confirm the data was collected honestly. The gathered data were then consolidated, with proof provided by the returned survey questionnaires. Subsequently, the data were tallied, analyzed, and interpreted statistically. The following statistical tools were used to interpret the gathered

data: the mean was used to determine the levels of work values, work-life balance, and alternative work arrangements, addressing the first three research objectives. Pearson's *r* was employed to assess the significance of the relationship between alternative work arrangements and work values, as well as between alternative work arrangements and work-life balance, addressing the fourth objective. Regression Analysis was utilized to determine the influence of alternative work arrangements on the work values and work-life balance of teachers.

2.5. Ethical Considerations —In conducting the study, the researcher followed necessary steps starting in October 2022. Initially, permission was sought from the Dean of the Graduate School to officially acknowledge the research by the university. This approval was then sent to the Schools Division Superintendent, District Supervisor, and School Heads of the identified schools as venues for the study. The letter requested permission to conduct research on the influence of work values and work-life balance on teachers' alternative work arrangements. The Certificate of Approval, or Form 2.6, was sent via UMERC email to the researcher with UMERC number 2023-116. Upon receiving approval from the relevant personnel and the

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3. Results and Discussion

The study includes a detailed presentation of the gathered data, along with a comprehensive discussion, interpretation, and implications of the findings. It describes the levels of work values, work-life balance, and alternative work arrangements. Additionally, it illustrates the correlations between work values and alternative work arrangements, as well as between work-life balance and alternative work arrangements. The third section examines the extent to which predictor variables influence alternative work arrangements.

3.1. Level of Work Values Table 1 presents the level of work values, measured by six indicators: intrinsic values, organization-man-ethic, upward striving, social status of the job, conventional ethic, and attitude toward earnings. These indicators reflect the importance teachers place on their work. The overall mean rating for these work values was 4.38, indicating a very high level. This suggests that teachers consistently exhibit work values related to intrinsic values, organization-man-ethic, upward striving, social status of the job, conventional ethic, and attitude toward earnings. The table reveals that the so-

cial status of the job had the highest mean rating of 4.42, followed closely by conventional ethic at 4.41, intrinsic values at 4.39, organization-man-ethic and upward striving both at 4.36, and attitude toward earnings at 4.34, all rated very high. The very high overall result of work values suggests that teachers remain engaged in their jobs, making their workdays pass quickly compared to idling. They view teaching as a highly respected profession in their community, which motivates them to stay in the field. Additionally, they work diligently with the hope of achieving promotions to higher-level positions.

This finding aligns with Giray's (2021) assertion that work values are crucial to an employee's success. In the educational sector, a teacher's success can also be attributed to their work values. Teaching involves interacting with diverse individuals who exhibit various behaviors (Tran, 2020). It is a challenging job, especially when unexpected situations arise that test

a teacher's ability to handle them (Rajendran et al., 2020). Moreover, the findings support Zhang's (2021) perspective that values are not merely about one's capacity to handle pressure, demands, and frustrations. Instead, values are beliefs or convictions that shape our lives and significantly influence our approach to work.

3.2. Level of Work-Life Balance Presented

Table 1. *Level of Work Values*

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Intrinsic Values	0.467	4.39	Very High
Organization-Man Ethic	0.406	4.36	Very High
Upward Striving	0.538	4.36	Very High
Social Status of Job	0.461	4.42	Very High
Conventional Ethic	0.436	4.41	Very High
Attitude toward Earnings	0.587	4.34	Very High
Overall	0.416	4.38	Very High

in Table 2 is the level of work-life balance of teachers. This is composed of five indicators namely: satisfaction with family and self-life, role overload, awareness, job satisfaction and flexible environment, and self-appreciation of work. The five domains of work-life balance had an overall mean of 4.33 or strongly agree which implies that the domains are manifested all the time.

Table 2. *Level of Work Life-Balance*

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Satisfaction with Family and Self-Life	0.453	4.38	Very High
Role Overload	0.478	4.35	Very High
Awareness	0.419	4.36	Very High
Job Satisfaction and Flexible Environment	0.271	4.16	High
Self-Appreciation of Work	0.423	4.39	Very High
Overall	0.300	4.33	Very High

Among the five construct, self-appreciation of work had the highest mean with a rating of 4.39 or strongly agree, followed by satisfaction with family and self-life with a mean score of 4.38 or strongly agree, awareness had a mean of 4.36 or strongly agree, role overload had a mean of 4.35 or strongly agree, and the lowest is job satisfaction and flexible environment with a mean rating of 4.16 or agree. The very high level of instructional management strategy is supported by the statements in the appended tables of work-life balance. It was noted that teachers perform effectively and are not hindered by family issues. They view their work as essential for survival and believe that achieving work-life balance will make them more effective and successful. This finding aligns with Punah and Kamboj's (2019) assertion that work-life balance is crucial for enhancing teacher effectiveness and satisfaction in student learning. A good quality of work-life balance has consistently been shown to improve teacher wellness and student behavior and performance. Similarly, Hill et al., (2021) argue that work-life balance is the ability to balance the emotional, behavioral, and time demands of work, family, and personal duties. It involves giving the right amount of time and effort to both work and personal life. Work-life balance is achieved when an individual's right to a fulfilling life inside

and outside of work is respected. Additionally, Javier and Rosal (2021) found that for teachers to be productive and enhance student learning, a healthy work-life balance is essential. It benefits both the school and the students' overall welfare. Work-life balance not only makes a job more satisfying but also encourages teachers to remain in educational institutions longer.

3.3. Level of Alternative Work Arrangements – Table 3 displays the level of alternative work arrangements for teachers, measured by

four indicators: hours worked per week, schedule flexibility, work from home, and irregular schedule. The overall mean rating was 4.36, described as very high. This high rating was derived from the individual ratings of the four indicators: work from home had a mean rating of 4.46, hours worked per week had a mean rating of 4.38, schedule flexibility had a mean rating of 4.31, and irregular schedule had a mean rating of 4.29, all rated very high.

Table 3. Level of Alternative Work Arrangement

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Hours Work Per Week	0.430	4.38	Very High
Schedule Flexibility	0.355	4.31	Very High
Work From Home	0.538	4.46	Very High
Irregular Schedule	0.340	4.29	Very High
Overall	0.378	4.36	Very High

The very high level of alternative work arrangements is attributed to the flexibility teachers have in choosing their work times and days. This implies that teachers have the autonomy to fit their work into their schedules. Additionally, teachers can perform work from home beyond their formal job requirements, adhering to formal work schedules at home. The findings also indicated that teachers believed they could remain productive while on alternative work arrangements (Seguritan, 2021). Furthermore, teachers agreed that alternative work arrangements contributed to a better balance between family and work life (Tacadao, 2020).

3.4. Significance on the Relationship between Levels of Work Values and Alternative Work Arrangements – The data in Table 4 showed the correlation between work values and alternative work arrangements. It can be perceived from the overall results that there was no significant relationship between work val-

ues and alternative work higher than 0.05 and its correlation coefficient r -value is $-.076$. The null hypothesis that there was no significant relationship between work values and alternative work arrangements is therefore accepted. It could be observed that work values does not affect alternative work arrangements of teachers. The findings emphasized that there was no significant relationship between work values and alternative work arrangements. The overall results indicate no significant relationship between work values and alternative work arrangements, with a p -value higher than 0.05 and a correlation coefficient (r -value) of -0.076 . Therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between work values and alternative work arrangements is accepted. This suggests that work values do not influence the alternative work arrangements of teachers.

Table 4. Significance of the Relationship between the Work Values and Alternative Work Arrangements

Work Values	Hours Work Per Week	Schedule Flexibility	Work Home	From Irregular Schedule	Overall
Intrinsic Values	-0.313* (0.000)	-0.181* (0.003)	-0.133* (0.029)	-0.250* (0.000)	-0.235* (0.000)
Organization-Man Ethic	-0.221* (0.000)	-0.238* (0.000)	-0.215* (0.000)	-0.256* (0.000)	-0.253* (0.000)
Upward Striving	-0.024 (0.694)	-0.055 (0.369)	0.011 (0.861)	0.083 (0.172)	0.004 (0.946)
Social Status of Job	0.013 (0.833)	-0.081 (0.187)	-0.028 (0.647)	0.042 (0.491)	-0.014 (0.814)
Conventional Ethic	-0.015 (0.805)	-0.115 (0.060)	-0.135* (0.026)	-0.054 (0.380)	-0.090 (0.139)
Attitude toward Earnings	0.102 (0.095)	0.105 (0.086)	0.071 (0.248)	0.114 (0.062)	0.107 (0.079)
Overall	-0.073 (0.230)	-0.093 (0.127)	-0.070 (0.255)	-0.043 (0.486)	-0.076 (0.215)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level.

The findings highlight that there is no significant relationship between work values and alternative work arrangements. Among the six indicators of work values, intrinsic values and organization-man ethic showed significance with p-values of 0.000 and r-values of -0.235 and -0.253, respectively. However, when the four indicators of alternative work arrangements were correlated with work values, no construct showed significance. This implies that all domains of alternative work arrangements do not affect the overall work values of teachers. The findings of Realon (2019) suggest a positive impact of alternative work arrangements on workers' motivation, performance, retention, and work values, which is relevant to this study. Flexible work hours, considered the optimal alternative work arrangement for both employees and managers, showed improved achievement among teachers. Additionally, Spreitzer et al., (2019) emphasized that workers tend to choose

increasingly flexible work schedules, allowing them to work without being hindered by obstacles such as traffic or household chores. Kossek and Michel (2019) found that millennials are more likely to accept job offers from companies that offer flexible work schedules, as this allows them to spend time on other tasks and earn additional income.

3.5. Significance on the Relationship between the Work-Life Balance and Alternative Work Arrangements – Similarly, Table 5 presents the relationship between work-life balance and alternative work arrangements, showing an overall p-value of 0.000, which is below the study's threshold, and an r-value of 0.400. This indicates that work-life balance significantly affects alternative work arrangements. Consequently, the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between work-life balance and alternative work arrangements is rejected. The findings highlight a significant re-

relationship between work-life balance and alternative work arrangements. Among the domains of work-life balance, five out of six show correlations with overall alternative work arrangements: role overload (p-value of 0.001, r-value of 0.202), awareness (p-value of 0.007, r-value of 0.165), job satisfaction (p-value of 0.001, r-value of 0.196), self-appreciation (p-value of 0.000, r-value of 0.867), and job satisfaction and flexible environment (p-value of 0.001, r-value of 0.165). These results indicate that the associations between role overload, awareness, job satisfaction, flexible environment, and self-

appreciation with overall alternative work arrangements were observed among teachers. Additionally, when the domains of alternative work arrangements were correlated with work-life balance, all domains showed a significant relationship. The data shows that hours worked per week have a p-value of 0.000 and a correlation coefficient (r-value) of 0.327, schedule flexibility has a p-value of 0.000 and an r-value of 0.395, work from home has a p-value of 0.000 and an r-value of 0.328, and irregular schedule has a p-value of 0.000 and an r-value of 0.423.

Table 5. Significance of the Relationship between Work-Life Balance and Alternative Work Arrangements

Work-Life Balance	Hours Work Per Week	Schedule Flexibility	Work From Home	Irregular Schedule	Overall
Satisfaction with Family and Self-Life	0.041 (0.503)	-0.005 (0.932)	0.013 (0.829)	0.116 (0.056)	0.043 (0.478)
Role Overload	0.149* (0.014)	0.189* (0.002)	0.141* (0.020)	0.279* (0.000)	0.202* (0.001)
Awareness	0.107 (0.079)	0.165* (0.007)	0.117 (0.055)	0.231* (0.000)	0.165* (0.007)
Job Satisfaction and Flexible Environment	0.134* (0.028)	0.265* (0.000)	0.140* (0.021)	0.201* (0.001)	0.196* (0.001)
Self-Appreciation of Work	0.769* (0.000)	0.870* (0.000)	0.793* (0.000)	0.713* (0.000)	0.867* (0.000)
Overall	0.327* (0.000)	0.395* (0.000)	0.328* (0.000)	0.423* (0.000)	0.400* (0.000)

**Significant at 0.05 significance level.*

These findings support Sangarandeniya and Ranasinghe’s (2020) argument that high employee turnover leads to significant replacement and start-up costs for companies. Therefore, ensuring the happiness of the current workforce is crucial. Both employees and organizations benefit from a well-balanced work and family

life. One way to manage a healthy work-life balance within an organization is by offering alternative work arrangements. Shagvaliyeva and Yazdanifard (2020) affirm this, revealing that alternative work arrangements promote and facilitate work-life balance. They also noted that offering such arrangements reduces stress

and increases employee well-being, which are outcomes of a balanced work-life.

3.6. Extent of Influence of Predictor Variables on Alternative Work Arrangements – Table 6 presents the regression coefficients used to test the significant influence of overall work values and work-life balance on alternative work arrangements. The regression analysis revealed that work values and work-life balance significantly influence alternative work arrangements, with an F value of 71.614 and a p-value less than 0.05. The R² value of 0.349 indicates that 34.9 of the variation in work values and work-life balance is due to alternative work arrangements, while the remaining 65.1 is influenced by other factors not covered in this study. The p-value less than 0.05 leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis set earlier in the study. Specifically, the data showed that work values and work-life balance significantly influence alternative work

arrangements, with p-values of 0.000, which are less than the alpha value of 0.05. Among these, work-life balance has the highest beta coefficient of 0.962, indicating it has the most substantial influence on alternative work arrangements. However, work values can also influence alternative work arrangements when supported by other variables. This implies that both work values and work-life balance affect teachers' choices regarding alternative work arrangements. In the realm of organizational behavior, social exchange theory is often employed to elucidate how interpersonal relationships between employees and employers are formed and sustained, particularly in terms of reciprocation processes (Rawshdeh et al., 2019). This theory sheds light on the reasons behind varying levels of employee engagement and how organizational support systems can foster creativity and other positive behaviors among subordinates.

Table 6. The Extent of Influence of Predictor Variables on Alternative Work Arrangements

Independent Variables	(Standardized Coefficients)	B (Unstandardized Coefficients)	T	Sig.
Constant	—	2.458	9.065	.000
Work Values (WV)	-0.568	-0.517	-8.810	.000
Work-Life Balance (WLB)	0.765	0.962	11.869	.000
R		0.591		
R²		0.349		
F		71.614		
P		.000		

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the findings, conclusion and recommendation based on the results of the data analyzed, discussed, and drawn implications. Findings are based on the posed statement of

the problem; conclusions are based on the findings generated and recommendations are based on the implications of the discussions.

4.1. Findings—The study’s findings were bolstered using regression analysis, which enabled the examination of correlations and regression. This approach identified which specific predictor variables influenced alternative work arrangements. The results indicated that the levels of work values, work-life balance, and alternative work arrangements were all very high, suggesting that the survey items were well-represented. No correlation was found between work values and alternative work arrangements. However, a significant relationship was observed between work-life balance and alternative work arrangements, with work-life balance having the strongest influence. This highlights the substantial impact of work-life balance on alternative work arrangements. The preference for alternative work arrangements can be attributed to various factors, some of which may have been explored in other studies regarding teachers’ work values and work-life balance. It is plausible that other influential factors were not included in this study. The findings align with Alderfer’s (1969) ERG theory, which emphasizes needs such as existence, relatedness, and growth. According to the theory, dissatisfaction with the current work plan can lead to an imbalance and negative work values. The study’s first objective was to assess the level of work values. Among the six indicators, attitude toward earnings was the lowest, though still rated as strongly agree. Another finding revealed that job satisfaction and a flexible environment had the lowest ratings in terms of work-life balance, though still rated as agree.

4.2. Conclusions—This suggests a need to focus on improving student achievement, as it significantly impacts both teachers’ and schools’

performance. Teachers should maximize their working time to enhance learning outcomes, and school heads should monitor and evaluate teachers’ performance based on their work plans. Work-life balance, in its singular capacity, significantly influenced alternative work arrangements, having the highest beta coefficient. The study also found that teachers strongly agreed with the level of alternative work arrangements, indicating their openness to various schedules. However, irregular schedules received the lowest rating, suggesting a preference for regular work schedules. No significant relationship was found between work values and alternative work arrangements.

4.3. Recommendations—The Department of Education could initiate programs to motivate teachers to stay in their jobs and perform excellently. Providing necessary resources and strengthening the reward system could boost teachers’ interest in teaching. It was suggested that the Department of Education review the qualifications for teachers applying for Alternative Work Arrangements (AWA) and develop a localized monitoring tool for those in AWA. School heads should plan activities that place teachers on specific schedules to ensure they perform their duties effectively. School leaders should help teachers by reducing non-teaching tasks to allow them to focus on their primary duty of teaching. The researcher recommends that the Department of Education develop programs to strengthen work-life balance, guiding teachers to improve their performance. Further research on other factors associated with alternative work arrangements is also recommended to validate the current study’s findings. Future studies could use both quantitative and qualitative methods to confirm these results.

5. References

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